

Classification of Balinese Passive Verbs: Morphological Study

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Article history:

Received: January, 02, 2022; Accepted: April, 01, 2023; Displayed Online: April, 11, 2023; Published: June, 30, 2023

Keywords

Verb;

Passive;

Morphology;

Balinese;

Linguistics;

Abstract

Research on the Classification of Passive Verbs in Balinese as morphological study, in general, is expected to contribute to the preservation and development of the Balinese language. In addition, this research is expected to contribute linguistic facts about the Balinese language. It specifically aims to discuss issues related to morphological aspects, that is about how the classification of Balinese passive verbs from their morphological studies. In addition to the use of structural theory, this research is also completed with morphological theory proposed by Kridalaksana and Ramlan. The classification of passive verbs in Balinese was found to be categorized as transitive and intransitive verbs. Intransitive verbs are divided into reflexive and stative intransitive verbs. The category of nouns is further differentiated into nouns denoting the results of a process, nouns denoting professions, and nouns denoting tools. The category of adjectives is divided into graded qualitative adjectives which are further classified into character-describing adjectives, size adjectives, color adjectives, mental attitude adjectives, and perception adjectives, as well as ungraded classificatory adjectives. The numerals category is divided into principal numerals and level numerals. Furthermore, the principal numerals are differentiated into definite numerals (including the numeral of whole number and fractions) and indefinite numerals.

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1. Introduction

Balinese language is still growing and developing until now. Balinese language serves as a medium of communication for its speakers to learn, live and express Balinese cultural values. In its position as a regional language, Balinese serves as a means of oral communication, especially in formal relationships, such as conversations in the family environment, conversations between individuals in Balinese society in relation to unofficial topics, conversations between members of the community in intimate relationships, and conversations between individuals in Balinese society in relation to regional topics. Balinese is also a tool for developing regional language and culture, as well as a tool for developing a national language (Cf. Bagus, 1988:13).

In addition, the Balinese language also plays an important role as a written communication tool. The Balinese language remains a powerful tool for developing Balinese literary works and other arts, such as drama, *wayang* (traditional puppet), dance and *arja* (traditional performance). The regional arts are supported by the use of the Balinese language which is regulated in such a way as to foster artistic charisma. In addition, the Balinese language is also used in customs, religion (especially Hinduism), and social organizations, and others. In short, the Balinese language remains a potential asset which is as an element and also as a vehicle for Balinese culture.

In relation to Indonesian, Balinese is a potential support to the development of Indonesian. Many Balinese terms are not found in Indonesian. The terms in question, are especially terms related to art, customs, religion, and social organizations in Bali. These terms have potential support to enrich the Indonesian vocabulary. Thus, the Balinese language is as an element and vehicle for Balinese culture, which also means the nation's (Indonesian) cultural wealth as well as supporting the development of the Indonesian language, and it deserves attention. One form of attention can be in the form of research on the Balinese language.

Such widespread use of the Balinese language creates a sense of pride and it motivates the community to maintain the Balinese language. Efforts to maintain and take steps to foster, preserve and develop the Balinese language are manifested through efforts such as the Balinese Language Dictionary and Balinese Grammar. Other efforts were carried out by holding competitions for writing novels and short stories or regional literary contests organized by Listibiya of the Province of Bali. In this regard, the Balinese language needs to be maintained so that it is still able to carry out the cultural expressions of its people. For this reason, research on the Balinese language as a form of concern for the Balinese language is urgently needed.

In connection with the above, research that specifically concerns on one aspect of language has not been carried out much. This prompted the author to raise aspects of the Balinese language, especially the Classification of Balinese Passive Verbs for Morphological Studies. Specifically, this study aims to describe the classification of Balinese passive verbs, with details including a description of the classification of Balinese passive verbs, nouns that become Balinese passive verbs, adjectives that become Balinese passive verbs and numerals that become Balinese passive verbs.

Generally, this research is expected to give contribution to the preservation and development of the Balinese language, although it is realized that this contribution is of a small scale. In addition, this research is expected to contribute linguistic facts about the Balinese language, especially in the field of morphology to serve as a basis for guidelines in using Balinese language; as a basis for further research on Balinese language; as a basis for determining the direction of the policy for fostering and developing the Balinese language.

2. Materials and Methods

The classification of Balinese passive verbs is the result of a morphological process, namely the addition of affixes (prefixes), so in this study besides using structural theory it is also equipped with morphological theory. Affixes are units of language related to subdivisions of linguistics, such as the field of morphology. Morphology is a part of linguistics that discusses or studies the intricacies of word forms and the effect of changes in word forms on the class and meaning of words (Ramlan, 1985:19). In accordance with this understanding of morphology, in essence, morphology investigates morphemes and arranges them into words and decomposes words into morphemes. Thus, the smallest element discussed in morphology is the morpheme and the largest element is the word.

Kridalaksana (1989:206) said that the most appropriate morphological description is a process model description. In this case, morphemes are treated as ingredients used in processing lexemes into words. Process in morphology by Ramlan (1985:46) is called morphological process. The morphological process is the process of forming words from other units which are the basic forms. Furthermore, the basic forms can be words or main words. The morphological process is described in the morphological system as follows (Kridalaksana, 1989:12).

Chart: Morphology

Lexeme -----> morphological process -----> word

The chart above shows that words are formed through morphological processes. The morphological process occurs from the input, namely lexemes and the output is in the form of words. Lexeme as the basic form in the morphological process, according to Kridalaksana (1989:9), is the basic unit of the lexicon. Meanwhile, the morphological process itself can be in the form of (1) zero derivation, (2) affixation, (3) reduplication, (4) abbreviation (shortening), (5) composition (combination), and (6) reverse derivation (Kridalaksana, 1989:12).

Furthermore, words as a result of morphological process in a language have various forms and often undergo changes. These changes often lead to changes in class and meaning of words. Such changes are common events in language and occur consistently (according to principles), so that they can be referred to as a system in language, likewise the classification of passive verbs in Balinese.

In collecting data, the method of listening is used (Sudaryanto, 1993: 132). It is called the listening method because it is done by listening to the use of language (the use of the Balinese passive verb that has been set). Next, all the Balinese passive verb data are recorded into the data card.

Distributional method (Sudaryanto, 1993:15) is used in analyzing the data. The distributional method is carried out by connecting phenomena in the language itself without connecting it with things outside the language. This method has the basic technique of segmenting immediate constituent. The method in analyzing the data is by classifying the collected data, analyzing them based on basic techniques for immediate constituent (Sudaryanto, 1993:31). Furthermore, the basic techniques for segmenting immediate constituent are assisted by advanced techniques, such as deletion, substitution, and expansion (Sudaryanto, 1993:36-37).

After the analysis, it was found that the rules were presented using informal and formal methods. The informal presentation method is formulation with ordinary words, while the formal presentation method is formulation with signs and symbols, such as arrows, curly brackets, asterisks, letter symbols as name abbreviations, and various diagrams (Sudaryanto, 1993: 145), assisted by induction and deduction techniques.

3. Results and Discussions

In this paper, each category of passive verbs will be classified in more detail. The purpose of this classification is to determine the derivational ability of a word category, to be formed into a passive verb. In addition, the classification is also to find out the detailed meaning of Balinese passive verbs. It should be added that the passive verb can be added with the prefix *-ka* combined with the suffix *-in* or *-ang*. The classification of passive verbs found in the data is verbs, nouns, adjectives, and numerals; they are as follows.

3.1 Verb Classification

The categories of verbs that become passive verbs, broadly speaking, can be grouped into two kinds, namely transitive verbs and intransitive verbs. The two types of verbs will be described in the following descriptions.

(1) Transitive Verbs

Transitive verbs are verbs that have or require objects in sentences (Kridalaksana, 1986:50). Alwi et al. (1993:97) says that a transitive verb is one that requires a noun as an object in an active sentence and that object can function as a subject in a passive sentence. It means that a transitive verb is a verb that functions as a predicate in a sentence that has an object. This type of verb can be exemplified below.

tutug 'follow'

aba 'bring'

lantig 'hit'

The above words can be used in the following sentences.

(1) *Tutug adine mulih, Yan!*

'Follow your sister home, Yan!'

Aba bungane ke peken, Luh

'Bring those flowers to the market, Luh!'

Lantig lelipine aji kayu, De!

'Hit the snake with the stick, De!'

The examples of above sentences are active sentences that have transitive basic verb predicates, such as *tutug* 'follow', *aba* 'bring', and *lantig* 'hit'. These words are called transitive basic verbs because the words *tutug* 'follow', *aba* 'bring', and *lantig* 'hit' always require the presence of a noun as an object after them. Furthermore, the object will function as a subject in the passive sentence.

These forms can be used in passive sentence, that is by adding an affix, such as the prefix *ka-* in front of the verb. Thus, these forms will become passive verbs, such as *katutug* 'followed', *kaaba* 'brought', and *kalantig* 'hit'. The use of passive verbs can be seen in the following sentences.

(2) *Nyoman Santosa katutug baan memene ka paon.*

'Nyoman Santosa was followed by his mother into the kitchen'

Bungane suba kaaba ke peken.

'The flowers have already been brought to the market'

Lelipine suba kalantig aji kayu.

'The snake had been beaten with a stick'

(2) Intransitive Verbs

Intransitive verbs are verbs that avoid objects (Kridalaksana, 1986:50). This opinion is in line with the notion that intransitive verbs are verbs that function as predicates that do not have an object in a sentence. In Balinese, as shown in the collected data, intransitive verbs that can be used as passive verbs are grouped into two types, namely reflexive verbs and stative verbs. The clarity of the two verbs is presented in the description as follows.

(2a) Reflexive Verbs

Reflexive verbs are verbs that are used together with reflexive pronouns. In Indonesian, reflexive verbs without pronouns are found, for example *mandi* 'bath' (Kridalaksana, 1982:177). Reflexive verbs can be equated with verbs in which the presence of the subject simultaneously receives the result of the action stated by the verb. In Balinese, there are examples of reflexive verbs, such as *kayeh* 'bath', *raup* 'wash face', *ambuh* 'wash hair', and *wasuh* 'wash'.

The word *kayeh* 'bath', *raup* 'wash face', and the word *ambuh* 'wash hair', if changed into a passive verb, must be added with the prefix *ka-* which combines with the suffix *-ang* or *-in*. Thus, formations were found such as *kayehang* 'washed', *karaupin* 'washed face', and *kaambuhin* 'washed hair'.

(2b) Stative verbs

Stative verbs are verbs that cannot be accompanied by moderate auxiliary words, for example in Indonesian the word *menyerupai* 'resembles', *menyamai* 'equals' (Kridalaksana, 1982:177). Stative verbs can also be said to be verbs that have similarities with adjectives. In Balinese, examples of stative verbs are *idup* 'alive' and *mati* 'dead'. The words *mati* 'dead' and *idup* 'alive' can be used as passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* or *ka-* combined with the suffix *-ang*. Thus, formations were found such as *kamatiang* 'killed' and *kaidupang* 'turned on'.

3.2 Noun Classification

Nouns as passive verbs in Balinese can at least be classified into three types, namely (1) nouns denoting the result of a process, (2) nouns denoting profession, and (3) nouns denoting tools. The three types of nouns above are described as in the following presentation.

(1) Noun denoting the result of a process

Nouns denoting the result of a process can be classified into two types, namely nouns denoting the results of non-natural processes and nouns denoting the results of natural processes. Nouns denoting the results of non-natural processes are divided into two kinds, they are names of arts and crafts and names of buildings.

(a) Non-Natural Processed Nouns

(a1) Craft Name

Nouns denoting the results of non-natural processes from arts and crafts are *batik* 'batik', *potrek* 'portraits/photos', and *gambar* 'pictures'. These words can be used as passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-*, so that the forms are found like *kabatik* 'made to be batik', *kapotrek* 'portraised/photographed', and *kagambar* 'drawn'. But no such formations as **kabatikin*, **kabatikang*, and **kapotrekang*, **kapotrekin* were found. This shows that the words *batik* and *potrek* can only be added with the prefix *ka-*.

Meanwhile, the prefix *ka-* can be added to the word *gambar* and can also be added to the prefix *ka-* which is joined with the suffix *-ang* or *-in*, so that you can find forms such as *kagambarin* 'drawn' and *kagambarang* 'depicted'.

(a2) Building Name

Nouns denoting the result of a non-natural process of building names can be exemplified by *kreteg* 'bridge', *ampik* 'porch', and *kamar* 'room'. These words can be used as passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* combined with the suffix *-in*. So that some forms were found such as *kakamarin* 'a room was made', *kakretegin* 'a bridge was made', and *kaampikin* 'a porch was given'. However, no formations such as **kakamar*, **kakreteg*, and **kaampik* were found.

(b) Natural Processed Nouns

The examples of nouns denoting the results of natural processes are *entut* 'fart' and *enceh* 'pee'. These words can be added with the prefix *ka-* which is joined by the suffix *-in*. Thus, formations such as *kaentutin* 'farted' and *kaencehin* 'urinated' were found. However, no forms such as **kaentut* and **kaenceh* were found.

(2) Noun Denoting Profession

Nouns denoting professions in this paper are divided into four types, namely professions in the crime sector, professions in the education sector, professions in the transportation sector, and professions in the trade sector. The four kinds of nouns denoting the profession are described in the following examples.

(2a) Profession in the Field of Crime

The example of nouns denoting professions in the field of crime are *maling* 'thief' and *begal* 'robbers'. These words can be used as passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* or adding the affix combination *ka-...-an* to form the words *kabegal* 'robbed', *kamaling* 'stolen', and *kamalingan* 'theft'.

(2b) Profession in the Field of Education

The example of nouns denoting profession in the field of education are *guru* 'teacher', *rsi* 'priest', and *balian* 'shaman'. These words can be formed with the affix combination *ka-...-ang* or *ka-...-in*, but cannot be formed with the prefix *ka-* only. Thus, formations such as *kaguruang* 'called guru', *karsiang* 'called priest', and *kabalianin* 'treated by a shaman' were found. However, no formations of **kaguru*, **karsi*, and **kabalian* were found.

(2c) Profession in the Field of Transportation

The examples of noun denoting profession in the field of transportation are *sopir* 'driver', *kusir* 'coachman', and *kernet* 'driver's assistant'. These words can be formed with a combination of affixes *ka-...-in* and cannot be formed with prefix *ka-* only. Thus, formations of *kasopirin* 'the car is being driven by someone', *kakusirin* 'the horse-drawn carriage is being driven by someone', and *kakernetin* 'the driver is being assisted by someone' were found. However, no formations such as **kasupir*, **kakusir*, and **kakernet* were found.

(2d) Profession in the Field of Trade

There are not so many nouns denoting professions in the trade sector, for example *maklar* 'brokers', and *jagal* 'butchers' or 'animal slaughterers'. These words can be formed into passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* which is combined with the suffix *-in* such as *kamaklarin* 'brokered' and *kajagal* 'butchered'.

(3) Noun Denoting Tools

Nouns denoting tools in this paper are divided into four types, namely nouns denoting fittings, nouns denoting work tools, nouns denoting means of transportation, and nouns denoting weapons. The clarification of the four nouns is described below.

(3a) Fittings

The example of nouns denoting fittings are *cet* 'paint', *semen* 'cement', and *pletur* 'polish'. These words can be formed into passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* or you can add the prefix *ka-* combined with the suffix *-in*. Thus, formations of *kacet* 'painted', *kacetin* 'painted', *kasemen* 'cemented', *kasemenin* 'cemented', *kapletur* 'polished' and *kapleturin* 'polished' were found.

(3b) Working tool

The example of nouns denoting work tools are *gunting* 'scissors', *arit* 'sickles', and *tambah* 'hoe'. These words can be formed into passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-*, so that formations of *kagunting* 'cut by scissors', *kaarit* 'cut by sickles', and *katambah* 'dug with a hoe' were found.

(3c) Means of Transportation

The example of nouns denoting means of transportation are *grobag* 'crate', *dokar* 'gig', and *kapal* 'ship'. These words can be formed into passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* which combines with the suffix *-in*. Thus, several forms are found, such as *kagobagin* 'transported in wooden crates', *kadokarin* 'transported by carriage', and *kakapalin* 'transported' by ship'.

(3d) Weapon

The example of nouns denoting weapons are *bedil* 'rifle', *bom* 'bomb', and *panah* 'arrow'. These words can be formed into passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-*, so some formations are found, such as *kabedil* 'shot/shot', *kabom* 'bombed', and *kapanah* 'shot with arrows'.

3.3 Adjective Classification

The basic forms of adjectives that can form the basis of passive verbs in Balinese can be classified into two main types, namely graded qualitative adjectives and ungraded classificatory adjectives (compare with Alwi, 1993:189). Graded qualitative adjectives refer to the nature or referent quality of noun, verb, or other adjective. Meanwhile, ungraded adjectives identify referent of noun, or other forms, as elements of a group or class.

There are five kinds of qualitative adjectives, namely character-describing adjectives, size adjectives, color adjectives, mental attitude adjectives, and perception adjectives. The five kinds of graded qualitative adjectives and ungraded classificatory adjectives will be described as follows.

(1) Graded Qualitative Adjectives

(1a) Character-Describing adjectives

The examples of character-describing adjectives are *panes* 'hot', *dingin* 'cold', and *kedas* 'clean'. If these adjectives are used as passive verbs, they must be added with a combination of affixes *ka-...ang* or *ka-...-in*. Thus, some formations are found, such as *kapanesang* 'heated', *kapanesin* 'heated',

kadinginang 'cooled', and *kakedasang* 'cleaned'. However, no formations, such as **kapanes*, **kadingin*, or **kakedas* were found.

(1b) Size Adjective

Adjectives that express size refer to quantitative quality measurements, for example *tegeh* 'high', *cenik* 'small', and *joh* 'far'. If these words are used as passive verbs, you can add the affix combinations *ka-...-ang* or *ka-...-in*. Thus, some forms were found such as *kategehang* 'raised', *kacenicang* 'minimized', *kacenicin* 'scaled down', *kajohang* 'kept away', and *kajohin* 'shunned'. However, no formations such as **kategeh*, **kacenic* or **kajoh* were found.

(1c) Color Adjectives

The examples of adjectives that express color are *putih* 'white', *gadang* 'green', and *kuning* 'yellow'. These words can be used as passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* which combines with the suffix *-ang* or *-in*. Thus, some formations were found, such as *kaputihin* 'whiten', *kakuningin* 'yellowed', and *kagadangang* 'greened'. However, no formations such as **kaputih*, **kakuning*, or **kagadang* were found.

(1d) Mental Attitude Adjectives

Adjectives of mental attitude are related to mood disturbances or feelings, for example *sebet* 'sad', *demen* 'happy', and *nyeh* 'fear'. These words can be used as passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* combined with the suffix *-ang* or *-in*. Thus, some formations were found, such as *kasebetang* 'distressed', *kademenin* 'liked' and *kanyehin* 'feared'. However, no forms such as **kasebet*, **kademen* or **kanyeh* were found.

(1e) Perceptual Adjective

Perceptual adjectives are related to the five senses, for example *belus* 'wet', *pait* 'bitter', and *manis* 'sweet'. These words can be formed into passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* combined with the suffix *-ang* or *-in*. Thus, some formations were found, such as *kabelusin* 'wetted', *kapaitang* 'bitter', and *kamanisang* 'sweetened'. However, no formations, such as **kabelus*, **kapait*, or **kamanis* were found.

(2) Ungraded Classificatory Adjectives

Ungraded classificatory adjectives place the noun reference within a particular group or category. Its presence in an environment cannot be graded, so it is impossible to expand it with more, less, very (compare with Alwi, 1993:192). In Balinese, adjectives for this group are found, such as the words *genep* 'even' and *gasal* 'odd'

Words that are classified as ungraded classificatory adjectives can be formed into passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* which combines with the suffix *-ang*. Thus, some formations were found, such as *kagenepang* 'fulfilled' and *kagasalang* 'oddified'. No formations, such as **kagenep* or **kagasal* were found.

3.4 Numerical Classification

The numerals in this paper are classified into two types, namely numerals that indicate the principal and numerals that indicate the level. The two types of numerals are described as follows.

(1) Principal Numerals

Principal numerals can be further classified into two types, namely principal numerals which state a certain amount and principal numerals which state an indefinite amount. Numerals that state a certain amount are divided into two types, namely those that state the number of whole numbers and those that state the number of fractions.

The examples of numerals belong to a certain number of whole numbers are the word *besik* 'one' and *dadua* 'two'. These words can be used as passive verbs by adding the prefix *ka-* combined with the suffix *-ang* or *-in*. Thus, some formations were found, such as *kabesikang* 'to be used as one' and *kadaduanin* 'to be doubled (used with two hands)'. However, no formations such as **kabesik* or **kadadua* were found.

The examples of words belong to the number of fractions are *tenga* 'mid-half' and *prapat* 'quarter'. These words cannot be used as passive verbs because they are not found joined with the prefix *ka-* or their combination, so there are no forms such as **katenga*, **kaprapat*, or **katenganin* and **kaprapatang*.

The examples of indefinite numerals are *bedik* 'a little' and *liu* 'a lot'. These words were not found joined with the prefix *ka-* only, but were found joined with the prefix combination *ka-* and the suffix *-ang*. Thus, some formations were found, such as *kabedikang* 'reduced' and *kaliunang* 'increased'. However, no formations such as **kabedik* or **kaliu* were found.

(2) Level Numeral

Level numerals express order in number and structure, for example *pisan* 'one' becomes *kapisan* 'first', *tiga* 'three' becomes *katiga* 'third', and *pitu* 'seven' becomes *kapitu* 'seventh'. The level numeral that states sequence can only be added with the prefix *ka-*, but does not belong to the category of passive verbs.

Based on the explanation above, it turns out that passive verbs function as predicate fillers in Balinese passive sentence. In passive verbs, predicate fillers can be added with the prefix *ka-* or the prefix *ka-* combined with suffixes, for example *-ang* or *-in* and others.

4. Conclusion

Classification of the basic forms of Balinese passive verbs, were found to be categorized as transitive verbs and intransitive verbs. Intransitive verbs are divided into reflexive and stative intransitive verbs. The category of nouns is further differentiated into nouns denoting the results of a process, nouns denoting professions, and nouns denoting tools. The category of adjectives is divided into graded qualitative adjectives which are further classified into five types, namely character-describing adjectives, size adjectives, color adjectives, mental attitude adjectives, and perception adjectives, as well as ungraded classificatory adjectives. Finally, the numerals category is divided into principal numerals and level numerals. Furthermore, the principal numerals are differentiated into definite numerals (including the numeral of whole number and numeral of fractions) and indefinite numerals.

Acknowledgements

The current manuscript has no conflict of interest. The authors deliver their gratitude to the publisher of *GrowingScholar*, USA, which has accepted and published our work.

References

- Ardika, I W., et al.. (2013). *Sejarah Bali, dari Prasejarah Hingga Modern*. Denpasar: Udayana University Press.
- Bourdieu, Pierre. (1991). *Language and Symbolic Power*. USA: Harvard University
- Bourdieu, Pierre. (1995). *Outline of a Theory of Practice*. Cambridge: University Press
- Dwipayana, I. K. A. dan Gde S. A. (2018). *Hegemoni Hukum Adat Bali dalam Karya Sastra Berlatar Sosiokultural Bali*. *Jurnal Kajian Bali*, 08 (2) 85–105. <https://doi.org/10.24843/JKB.2018.v08.i02.p06>.
- Dwipayana, I. K. A. dan I. B. Bawa Adnyana. (2019). *Legitimasi Hukum Adat Bali dalam Karya Sastra Kultural*. *Retorika: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa, Sastra, dan Pengajarannya*, 12 (2): 208-222. <https://doi.org/10.26858/retorika.v12i2.9362>.
- Dwipayana, I.K.A dan N. Astawan. (2021). *The Domination of Patriarchism in Inheritance Customary Systems*. *Retorika: Jurnal, Bahasa, Sastra, dan Pengajarannya*. 14 (1) 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.26858/retorika.v14i1.13874>.
- Haryatmoko. (2007). *Etika Komunikasi: Manipulasi Media, Kekerasan dan Pornografi*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- Leech, G. (1993). *Prinsip-prinsip pragmatik [Pragmatic principles]*. Universitas Indonesia Press.
- N Arnawa, IW Gunartha, IN Sadwika. (2018). *Balinese Hegemonic Politness in Awig-Awig of Desa Pakraman*. *Theory & Practice in Language Studies*, 8 (11), 1485-1493. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17507/tpls.0811.13>.
- N Arnawa, IW Winaja, I Jaya Widanta. (2021). *Metaphors about Balinese Women: From Semantic Analysis to Cultural Pragmatic Interpretations*. *Language Related Research*, 12 (5), 239 – 277. <http://10.52547/LRR.12.5.10>.
- N Arnawa. (2022). *Linguistic devices in traditional forms of Balinese humour*. *Humour in Asian Cultures*, 62-87.
- Rusmini, O. (2000). *Tarian Bumi*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Rusmini, O. (2003). *Kenanga*. Jakarta: Grasindo.
- Sadnyini, I. A. (2016). *Sanksi Perkawinan Terlarang di Bali Dulu dan Kini*. Denpasar: Udayana University Press.
- Samarin, W. J. (1988). *Linguistik terapan [Field linguistics]*. Kanisius.
- Setia, Putu. (2014). *Bali Menggugat*. Jakarta: PT Gramedia.
- Shindu, N. R. (1969). *Ketika Kentongan Dipukul di Bale Banjar*. *Horison*, 1 (4): 27–29.
- Sobur, A. (2009). *Analisis Teks Media, Suatu Pengantar untuk Analisis Wacana, Analisis Semiotik, dan Analisis Framing*. Bandung: PT RemajaRosdakarya.
- Soethama, G. A. (2006). *Mandi Api*. Jakarta: Kompas.
- Suarka, N. (2019). *Penanaman Nilai Pendidikan Karakter melalui Seni Tembang Bali Tradisional*.
- Wijaya, P. (1971). *Bila Malam Bertambah Malam*. Jakarta: Pustaka Jaya.
- Windia, Wayan P. (2013). *Perkawinan Pada Gelahang di Bali*. Denpasar-Bali: Udayana University Press.
- Zainal, dkk. (2018). *Kekerasan Simbolik Dalam Tradisi Perkawinan Masyarakat Tolaki Sulawesi Tenggara*. *Jurnal Hasil-Hasil Penelitian*, 13 (2), 192-209. <http://dx.doi.org/10.31332/ai.v13i2.1068>.